

INFLUENCE OF TELEVISION ADVERTISING ON CONSUMER PURCHASING DECISIONS OF NESTLE MILO BEVERAGE IN SOUTH EAST NIGERIA

Ejim, Chizara Elizabeth

Department of Mass Communication
Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu

Abstract

The study evaluated the influence of television advertising on consumer purchasing decisions of Nestlé Milo beverage in South East Nigeria. Specifically, it assessed how appeal strategies used in television advertisements influence consumers' evaluation of alternatives, and examined the impact of branding elements in television advertising on consumer problem recognition. A survey research design was adopted with a sample of 360 respondents. Data were analyzed using correlation techniques. The findings revealed a significant and positive relationship between appeal strategies in television advertising and consumers' evaluation of alternatives ($r = .465, p < 0.01$). Similarly, branding elements in television advertising were found to have a significant and positive impact on consumer problem recognition ($r = .539, p < 0.01$). The study concludes that television advertising, through persuasive appeal strategies and consistent branding elements, plays a critical role in shaping consumer decision-making toward Nestlé Milo. It is recommended that Nestlé should sustain the use of strong advertising appeals and consistent branding cues in its television campaigns to reinforce consumer awareness and strengthen product preference.

Keywords: Television advertising, Consumer purchasing decisions

Introduction

Advertising is a vital tool in modern marketing, used to inform, persuade, and influence consumer behavior. Among its various forms, television advertising remains especially powerful due to its combination of sight, sound, and motion, making messages more impactful than print or audio alone (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Globally and in Nigeria, television continues to play a major role in shaping consumer attitudes and driving purchase decisions—particularly for fast-moving consumer goods (FMCGs) like food and beverages. In Nigeria, television reaches millions of households daily, making it a key platform for advertisers. For brands like *Nestlé Milo*—a popular malt-based cocoa drink consumed across age groups—TV advertising is central to maintaining market presence. Milo's campaigns often highlight themes such as nutrition, energy, sports, and family values, appealing to both children and parents (Ihechu, Anaba, & Ebele, 2022). Empirical studies have shown that Milo's television ads significantly influence household buying behavior. For instance, research in Aba found that children exposed to Milo commercials exerted pressure on parents to purchase the product. Similar studies in Uyo and Isiama Afara also reported increased brand awareness, preference, and consumer loyalty linked to repeated TV ad exposure (ResearchCage, 2017; ABUAD, 2014).

Despite these findings, gaps remain—especially in understanding how specific elements of Milo's television advertising (e.g., visuals, jingles, nutritional claims) affect purchasing decisions in the South-East region of Nigeria. This region, marked by rising urbanization, high literacy rates, and unique cultural values, presents a distinct media landscape that may shape consumer responses differently (Ihechu et al., 2022). Understanding these dynamics is crucial for both theory and practice. Academically, it enriches literature on advertising effectiveness in emerging markets. Practically, it

offers insights for Nestlé and other FMCG firms to tailor campaigns to regional audiences. It also informs policy and consumer advocacy, especially in guiding healthy consumption patterns.

This study, therefore, explores the influence of television advertising on household purchasing decisions for *Nestlé Milo* in South-East Nigeria. It aims to identify which ad components most effectively drive awareness, preference, and repeat purchases, offering strategic guidance to marketers and contributing to broader debates on consumer behavior and advertising regulation.

Statement of the Problem

In today's competitive business environment, advertising has become a crucial tool for shaping consumer perceptions and driving purchasing behavior. Television advertising, in particular, continues to hold significant influence in Nigeria due to its wide reach, audiovisual appeal, and ability to connect with diverse audiences. Beverage companies such as Nestlé Nigeria Plc invest heavily in promoting brands like Milo, emphasizing its nutritional value, energy-boosting qualities, and role in children's growth and development. Despite these efforts, the actual influence of such advertising on household purchasing decisions in South East Nigeria remains unclear.

While television advertisements are designed to stimulate interest and brand loyalty, several factors—such as household income, cultural preferences, competing brands, and consumer skepticism toward exaggerated claims—may weaken their impact. Furthermore, with the rise of alternative media platforms and changing consumer lifestyles, the effectiveness of traditional television advertising is increasingly questioned. In South East Nigeria, where households face varied socio-economic challenges, it is uncertain whether television advertising for Milo directly translates into increased household purchases or whether decisions are primarily driven by other considerations such as affordability, nutritional needs, or peer influence. The lack of empirical evidence on this relationship poses a problem for both marketers and policymakers. If advertising does not significantly influence consumer purchasing behavior, Nestlé's advertising strategies may not yield expected returns, and households may remain unresponsive to nutritional awareness campaigns embedded in such advertisements.

Therefore, the problem this study seeks to address is the extent to which television advertising influences consumer purchasing decisions of Nestlé Milo beverage in South East Nigeria. This inquiry is necessary to understand whether television advertisements achieve their intended purpose of shaping consumer behavior or whether other factors exert greater influence in household purchase decisions.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the influence of television advertising on consumer purchasing decisions of Nestle Milo Beverage in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Assess how appeal strategy used in television advertisements influence consumers' evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria.
- ii. Impact of branding elements in television advertising on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. How does appeal strategy used in television advertisements influence consumers' evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria?
- ii. What is the impact of branding elements in television advertising on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study:

- i. Appeal strategy used in television advertisements has no positive influence on consumers' evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria.
- ii. Branding elements in television advertising has no positive impact on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

This study focused on the influence of television advertising on consumer purchasing decisions of Nestlé Milo in South East Nigeria. It examined how appeal strategies affect consumers' evaluation of alternatives and how branding elements impact consumer problem recognition. The scope was limited to Milo beverage, television advertising as the medium, and consumers within the South East region.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Television Advertising

Television advertising involves creating and broadcasting commercials to promote products or services. Despite the rise of digital media, it remains highly effective due to its wide reach and sensory impact, with the average person spending around four hours daily watching TV (Aashish, 2023). This makes it a valuable platform for brand exposure. Ads typically run for 15 to 60 seconds during program breaks, ensuring high visibility. They may be produced in-house or through agencies, with media buying agencies managing their placement. Costs vary based on factors like duration, airtime, and program ratings. Effective ads use music, visuals, and special effects to engage viewers and must deliver clear messages quickly.

Television advertising takes several forms, including traditional commercials, product placements, brand integration, long-form infomercials, and short overlays during live broadcasts. Each format serves specific marketing objectives, from raising brand awareness to driving sales. Overall, television remains a persuasive advertising medium, combining entertainment with strategic messaging to influence consumer behavior effectively (Aashish, 2023).

Components of Television Advertising

Appeal Strategy

Appeal strategies in advertising are rhetorical techniques used to persuade audiences through credibility (ethos), logic (logos), or emotion (pathos). These approaches are often combined in television advertising to shape brand identity, influence consumer attitudes, and drive purchases. Ethos, or the appeal to credibility, is conveyed through endorsements by trusted figures or by highlighting a company's expertise. For example, health products often feature doctors or specialists to build trust. Credibility is essential in marketing, as it assures consumers the information is reliable (O'Shaughnessy & O'Shaughnessy, 2004). Logos appeals to logic by using facts, statistics, or demonstrations. In TV ads, this might involve product comparisons or test results, such as before-and-after visuals in cleaning product commercials. Logical appeals help consumers justify purchases, especially for practical or functional items (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Pathos, the emotional appeal, is widely used in television advertising. Through storytelling, visuals, music, and emotional scenarios, advertisers evoke feelings like happiness, nostalgia, or concern to create a stronger connection with the audience. Emotional narratives enhance consumer identification with brands and foster loyalty (Escalas & Bettman, 2005). By blending ethos to build trust, logos to provide rational support, and pathos to spark emotional connection, television advertising effectively engages both the logical and emotional sides of consumer decision-making.

Branding Elements

Branding elements are the distinctive features that help define, differentiate, and build associations with a brand in the minds of consumers. These elements work together to create a unified brand identity and play a crucial role in shaping consumer perception and loyalty. One fundamental branding element is the brand name, which serves as the primary verbal identifier of the product or company. According to Keller (2013), effective brand names are memorable, easy to pronounce, and aligned with the brand's positioning in the market. In addition to the name, logos and symbols act as visual identifiers that enhance recognition and build strong mental associations with the brand.

Taglines or slogans also serve as important branding tools. These short phrases capture the essence of the brand's promise, values, or unique selling proposition. A well-known example is Nike's "Just Do It," which has come to symbolize empowerment and motivation. Brand characters, such as mascots or animated figures, contribute personality and relatability, making the brand more engaging and emotionally appealing, as discussed by Kotler and Keller (2016).

Packaging plays a dual role by offering both functional protection and a visual representation of brand identity. Elements such as design, color, and typography on packaging influence consumer impressions at the point of purchase and help reinforce brand positioning. Underwood and Klein (2002) emphasize that packaging is often the first point of interaction between the consumer and the product, making it a vital component of branding.

Auditory branding elements, such as jingles and signature sounds, also contribute to brand recall and emotional connection. These sound cues can trigger instant recognition and positive associations in the minds of consumers. When applied consistently, these branding elements collectively establish a distinctive and coherent brand image. They enhance brand equity by making the brand easily recognizable, emotionally meaningful, and trustworthy across different consumer touchpoints, ultimately fostering long-term customer loyalty.

Consumer Purchasing Decisions

Consumer purchasing decisions refer to the processes and factors that influence how individuals choose, buy, use, and evaluate products or services. These decisions are shaped by a combination of psychological, social, cultural, and economic factors, and understanding them is central to marketing and consumer behavior research. A commonly cited framework is the **five-stage decision-making process**: problem recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decision, and post-purchase behavior (Kotler & Keller, 2016). In the first stage, consumers recognize a need, followed by actively seeking information about possible solutions. They then evaluate different options based on attributes such as price, quality, or brand reputation before making a purchase. Finally, post-purchase evaluations (e.g., satisfaction or dissatisfaction) influence future buying behavior and brand loyalty.

Psychological factors also play a key role. Motivation, perception, learning, and attitudes affect how consumers interpret information and make decisions. For instance, Maslow's hierarchy of needs suggests that consumers' purchasing priorities often depend on whether they are seeking basic necessities or self-actualization products (Solomon, 2018).

In addition, **social and cultural influences**—such as family, peer groups, and cultural values—significantly shape purchasing behavior. Studies show that reference groups can influence product choices, particularly in categories linked to status or identity (Bearden & Etzel, 1982). Similarly, cultural norms and traditions impact preferences in areas like food, fashion, and lifestyle. Finally, **situational factors**, including economic conditions and technological innovations, affect purchasing decisions. For example, digital platforms and online reviews increasingly guide consumers' evaluation of alternatives and purchase choices (Grewal et al., 2020). Understanding these

multifaceted influences allows businesses to design marketing strategies that align with consumer motivations and decision-making patterns, ultimately guiding customers from recognition of need to brand loyalty.

Components of Consumer purchasing decisions

Consumers' Evaluation of Alternatives

Consumers' evaluation of alternatives is a critical stage in the decision-making process, occurring after the information search and before the purchase decision. At this stage, consumers compare available options to determine which product or service best satisfies their needs and preferences. This evaluation is influenced by both objective and subjective criteria, as well as internal and external factors. According to Kotler and Keller (2016), consumers rely on evaluative criteria, which may include price, quality, brand reputation, features, and design. These criteria differ across product categories and consumer segments. For example, while price may be the most important factor for budget-conscious consumers, brand prestige may carry more weight for status-oriented buyers. Consumers often use compensatory and non-compensatory decision rules when evaluating alternatives. In compensatory models, weaknesses in one attribute (e.g., higher price) can be offset by strengths in another (e.g., superior quality). In contrast, non-compensatory models involve strict cutoffs, such as rejecting any brand above a certain price threshold (Solomon, 2018). Social influences also play a role. Research shows that reference groups and word-of-mouth recommendations strongly affect how alternatives are perceived, especially for products tied to identity and lifestyle (Bearden & Etzel, 1982). In the digital era, online reviews and ratings serve as powerful evaluative tools, shaping consumer perceptions before purchase (Grewal et al., 2020). Overall, the evaluation of alternatives is not purely rational; it integrates cognitive assessments with emotional and social considerations. By understanding this process, marketers can better position their offerings to align with the criteria most relevant to their target consumers.

Consumer Problem Recognition

Consumer problem recognition is the first stage in the consumer decision-making process. It occurs when an individual perceives a gap between their current state and a desired state, creating a sense of need that motivates action. This recognition can be triggered by internal stimuli, such as hunger or personal dissatisfaction, or external stimuli, such as advertising, peer influence, or changes in life circumstances (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Problem recognition can be need-based or opportunity-based. Need-based recognition happens when consumers identify a deficiency that must be addressed, such as running out of groceries. Opportunity-based recognition occurs when consumers realize that a better option exists, such as upgrading to a more advanced smartphone. As Engel, Blackwell, and Miniard (1995) emphasize, recognizing problems is not always about survival needs but can also involve aspirational desires tied to self-image and lifestyle.

Marketers often play an active role in stimulating problem recognition. Through persuasive messages, symbolic appeals, and strategic positioning, advertisements highlight unmet needs or suggest new ones. Solomon (2018) notes that effective marketing often frames a product as the solution to a problem consumers may not have consciously recognized, such as emphasizing health benefits to encourage switching to organic foods. In sum, consumer problem recognition sets the foundation for the decision-making journey. Without identifying a problem, consumers are unlikely to move toward information search, evaluation of alternatives, and eventual purchase. Recognizing and shaping consumer needs is therefore central to marketing strategy.

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by cultivation theory by George Gerbner 1969.

Uses and Gratification Theory

The theory that has emerged in our discourse so far to help further argue our position is the Uses and Gratifications theory which was first used by Elihu Katz in 1959. Most communication researchers up

to the point were questioning “what do the media do to people?” However, Katz suggested asking the question. What do people do with media?” Uses and Gratification theory assure that the media audience have alternate choice to satisfy their needs therefore they seek out a media source that best fulfills their needs. This theory perceives the recipient as actively influencing the effect process, since he selectively chooses, attends to, perceives & retain the media messages on the basis of his/her needs, belief etc., that focus was thus shifted from media production and transmission functions to the media consumption function. Instead of asking “what kinds of effects occur under what conditions?” the question became “who uses which contents from which media under which condition and for what reasons?”

The theory discussed above conforms to the study because it’s purely audience centered and addresses needs like surveillance function, excitement, guidance, identification, and socialization and information acquisition. Every organisation engaged in various promotional techniques in order to achieve their aim and the set objective of the organisation. The assumption of the theory posit that most people are exposed to various media and contents in order to gratify their needs. Every organisation is fully aware of their target audience and what actually gratify their immediate needs and desire, these gives rise to the use of television media for various advert based on the effect and power carried by the television media and the amount of believability and lasting effect on the audience.

Empirical Review

Maghsoudi et al. (2017) conducted a study in Kerman to examine the impact of advertising on consumer buying behavior toward date oil seed, using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). The research employed a descriptive design with a sample size of 384 participants and used descriptive statistical methods. Findings revealed that advertising positively and significantly influences consumer attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and subjective norms related to buying behavior. Additionally, the study identified that both subjective norms and the outcome of advertising act as mediating factors in shaping consumer purchasing decisions. The researchers recommended recognizing the mediating role of advertising and subjective norms in influencing consumer behavior. Ikechukwu et al. (2017) conducted a study in Awka, Anambra State, to examine the effects of media advertising on consumers’ purchase intent, focusing on Hero Beer. The study aimed to explore how media advertisements affect consumer intent, attention, and interest, and whether different media types influence purchasing decisions. Using a sample size of 200 and a linear regression model, the findings showed that TV and radio advertisements significantly influenced consumers’ purchase intent. Additionally, radio and billboard ads had a strong impact on the AIDCA components (Attention, Interest, Desire, Conviction, and Action). The study concluded that radio and billboard media had the most influence on consumer behavior toward Hero Beer. It recommended applying the AIDCA model to evaluate media advertising effectiveness for other beer brands and suggested increased use of TV infomercials to boost Hero Beer sales.

Awan et al. (2018) studied the impact of advertising on consumer buying behavior regarding FMCGs in Southern Punjab, Pakistan, using cross-sectional data from 231 respondents. Using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis, the study found that advertising significantly influences consumer behavior and product choices. It recommended continuous monitoring of consumer behavior when designing advertisements.

Rahmi, Mohammad, and Shamshad (2020) examined the influence of emotional response, environmental cues, brand awareness, and sensory-stimulated advertising on consumer behavior using a survey design with a sample of 32. Multiple regression analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between all the independent variables and consumer buying behavior. The study suggested that advertisers should thoroughly understand consumer patterns to ensure effective targeting.

Shaza, Nuruland, and Afnani (2021) investigated factors affecting consumer behavior toward local food brands in Selangor, using data from 210 respondents via Google Forms and analyzed with SPSS. The findings showed that the Halal logo was the most influential factor, followed by price, product size, quantity, and packaging. The study recommended that local sellers use these insights to attract more customers.

Achuku and Abubakar (2023) analyzed the effect of television, radio, and outdoor advertising on consumer behavior in Katsina, Nigeria, using data from 550 participants. The study found that television ads had a significant positive effect, radio ads had a negative but significant effect, and outdoor ads had no significant impact. It concluded that while TV ads are influential, other factors like price, income, and product quality also shape buying behavior. It recommended increasing TV ad frequency for better consumer response.

Uguru (2023) explored how television commercials influence product patronage among sports fans in Enugu. With a sample of 400, the study found that fans were highly aware of Heineken's commercials and had a positive perception of them. However, it recommended a review of pricing strategies, noting that lower-priced alternatives might shift consumer loyalty in a struggling economy.

Methodology

The study was carried out to examine the influence of television advertising on consumer purchasing decisions of Nestle Milo beverage in South East, Nigeria. Attention was focused on the state capitals of the South East—Umuahia (Abia), Awka (Anambra), Abakaliki (Ebonyi), Enugu (Enugu State), and Owerri (Imo). The descriptive survey research design was used to conduct the investigation. The primary data was generated through the administration of questionnaire. Out of a population of 8,379,997 consumers, the sample size of 368 was chosen after applying the Freund and William’s formula for the determination of adequate sample size. 360 copies of the 368-questionnaire issued throughout the data collecting process were returned, indicating a 98 percent instrument return rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. Data was presented in frequency tables. Data was presented and analyzed by means score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. Pearson Correlation Coefficient Analysis was used to test the Hypotheses.

Data Analysis

Research Question One: How does appeal strategy used in television advertisements influence consumers’ evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria?

Table 4.1: How appeal strategy used in television advertisements influence consumers’ evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria

S/N		N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Television advertisements of Nestlé Milo use credible sources (e.g., athletes, nutritionists) that make me trust the product more than alternatives.	360	1.00	5.00	1333.00	3.7028	1.31543
2	The logical information (e.g., nutritional benefits, ingredients) presented in Milo advertisements influences how I compare it with other beverage brands	360	1.00	5.00	1219.00	3.3861	1.43312
3	The emotional appeals (e.g., family bonding, energy for children) in Milo advertisements strongly affect my evaluation of other available beverages	360	1.00	5.00	1396.00	3.8778	1.08243

4	Milo's advertisements make the brand appear more reliable and convincing compared to competitors.	360	1.00	5.00	1358.00	3.7722	1.29421
5	Overall, the appeal strategies in Milo advertisements guide my decision when evaluating alternative beverage options.	360	1.00	5.00	1356.00	3.7667	1.21779
	Valid N (listwise)	360					

Source: Field Survey 2025; SPSS 23.0 Output

Table 4.1 shows that Nestlé Milo's TV ads influence consumers' evaluation of alternatives through credible sources (mean=3.70), logical information (mean=3.39), and strong emotional appeals (mean=3.88). The ads make Milo appear more reliable (mean=3.77) and overall effectively guide consumers' decisions when comparing beverages (mean=3.77). Response variability was moderate.

Research Question Two: What is the impact of branding elements in television advertising on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria?

Table 4.2: Impact of branding elements in television advertising on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria.

S/N		N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	The brand name <i>Milo</i> in television advertisements helps me recognize my need for an energy-boosting beverage.	360	1.00	5.00	1338.00	3.7167	1.37131
2	Milo's logo and visual symbols in advertisements remind me of the product when I feel the need for a nutritional drink.	360	1.00	5.00	1337.00	3.7139	1.17011
3	The slogans and taglines used in Milo advertisements (e.g., highlighting strength and vitality) make me aware of gaps in my beverage choices	360	1.00	5.00	1399.00	3.8861	1.04272
4	The packaging and product visuals in Milo television ads make me realize when I should choose a healthier alternative	360	1.00	5.00	1415.00	3.9306	1.15059
5	The jingles and sounds in Milo advertisements create awareness of my need for a nourishing beverage option.	360	1.00	5.00	1320.00	3.6667	1.30992
	Valid N (listwise)	360					

Source: Field Survey 2025; SPSS 23.0 Output

Table 4.2 shows that Nestlé Milo's branding elements in TV ads effectively trigger consumer problem recognition. The brand name and logo both scored a mean of about 3.71, reminding consumers of their need for an energy-boosting or nutritional drink. Slogans and taglines raised awareness of gaps in beverage choices (mean=3.88), while packaging and visuals strongly prompted consideration of healthier options (mean=3.93). Jingles and sounds also contributed to this awareness (mean=3.67). Standard deviations indicate moderate response variability.

Testing of the Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: Appeal strategy used in television advertisements has no positive influence on consumers' evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria

Table 4.3: Correlations result for Appeal strategy used in television advertisements has no positive influence on consumers’ evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria

	Appeal strategy used in television advertisements has no positive influence on consumers’ evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria		consumers’ evaluation of alternatives
Appeal strategy used in television advertisements has no positive influence on consumers’ evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 360	.465** .000 360
consumers’ evaluation of alternatives	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.465** .000 360	1 360

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey 2024; SPSS 23.0 Output

Decision Rule: We accept the null hypothesis if the correlation coefficient significant is less than the significant value at 1% significant level of confidence.

The correlation value ($r = .465$, $N = 360$, $p = .000$) indicates a strong, positive, and statistically significant relationship between appeal strategies in television advertisements and consumers’ evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestlé Milo in South East Nigeria. Since the p-value is below the 1% significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This confirms that appeal strategies in TV ads positively influence consumers’ evaluation of alternatives for Nestlé Milo.

Hypothesis Two

Statement of hypothesis Two: Branding elements in television advertising has no positive impact on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria.

Table 4.4: Correlations result for branding elements in television advertising has no positive impact on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria.

	Branding elements in television advertising has no positive impact on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria.		consumer problem recognition
Branding elements in television advertising has no positive impact on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 360	.539** .000 360

consumer problem recognition	Pearson Correlation	.539**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	360	360

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey 2024; SPSS 23.0 Output

Decision Rule: We accept the null hypothesis if the correlation coefficient significant is less than the significant value at 1% significant level of confidence.

The correlation value ($r = .539$, $N = 360$, $p = .000$) shows a strong, positive, and statistically significant relationship between branding elements in television advertising and consumer problem recognition of Nestlé Milo in South East Nigeria. Since the p-value is below the 1% significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the alternative. This confirms that branding elements in TV ads positively impact consumer problem recognition of Nestlé Milo.

Discussion of Findings

Appeal Strategy Used in Television Advertisements and Consumers' Evaluation of Alternatives

The result of this study revealed a strong and positive correlation ($r = .465$, $p < 0.01$) between appeal strategies used in television advertisements and consumers' evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestlé Milo in South East Nigeria. This finding suggests that television advertising strategies such as emotional appeal, credibility, and logical reasoning significantly influence how consumers assess competing beverage options.

This outcome aligns with the work of Maghsoudi et al. (2017), who found that advertising has a significant and positive effect on consumer attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, thereby influencing buying behavior. Similarly, Ikechukwu et al. (2017) demonstrated that television and radio advertisements had a strong influence on consumers' purchase intent for Hero Beer, supporting the argument that appeal strategies in advertisements affect consumer evaluations. In the same vein, Awan et al. (2018) reported that advertising significantly shapes consumer behavior in the FMCG sector, reinforcing the relevance of persuasive advertising appeals. The present study's findings are also consistent with Rahmi et al. (2020), who observed that emotional responses, brand awareness, and sensory stimulation in advertisements positively influence buying behavior. Given that Nestlé Milo employs a mix of emotional appeals (e.g., family bonding), logical appeals (e.g., nutritional benefits), and credibility appeals (e.g., endorsements by athletes), these strategies appear to directly enhance consumers' evaluation of alternatives in favor of Milo in South East Nigeria.

Branding Elements in Television Advertising and Consumer Problem Recognition

The result also indicated a strong and positive correlation ($r = .539$, $p < 0.01$) between branding elements in television advertising and consumer problem recognition of Nestlé Milo in South East Nigeria. This suggests that elements such as brand name, logo, packaging, slogans, and jingles play a significant role in making consumers recognize their need for Milo as a beverage option.

This finding is consistent with Shaza et al. (2021), who discovered that branding cues such as the Halal logo, price, size, and packaging influenced consumer preferences for local food products. Similarly, Achuku and Abubakar (2023) reported that television advertising strongly influenced consumer behavior, with branding elements creating awareness and arousing interest in Ajinomoto Foods Nigeria. Additionally, Uguru (2023) showed that television commercials enhanced product patronage among sports fans by creating strong awareness and positive perceptions. Taken together, these studies confirm the present study's outcome that branding elements embedded in advertising not only help consumers identify their needs but also position the brand as a solution to those needs. In the case of Nestlé Milo, consistent use of recognizable elements such as its green packaging, energy-

driven slogans, and jingles contributes to problem recognition among consumers in South East Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The findings at the end of this study include the following:

- i. Appeal strategy used in television advertisements had positive influence on consumers' evaluation of alternatives when choosing Nestle Milo in South East Nigeria ($r = .465$, $N = 360$, $P = .000$).
- ii. Branding elements in television advertising had positive impact on consumer problem recognition of Nestle Milo beverage in South East Nigeria ($r = .539$, $N = 360$, $P = .000$).

Conclusions

This study found that advertising significantly influences consumer purchasing decisions for Nestlé Milo in South East Nigeria. Appeal strategies such as emotional, logical, and credibility cues positively shaped consumers' evaluation of alternatives, while branding elements like the Milo name, logo, packaging, slogans, and jingles enhanced problem recognition. Overall, effective advertising not only creates awareness but also guides consumer choice and strengthens brand preference.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

- Since appeal strategies in television advertisements significantly influence consumers' evaluation of alternatives, Nestlé should continue to employ strong emotional, logical, and credibility-based appeals in Milo adverts to sustain consumer preference over competing brands.
- Because branding elements such as name, logo, packaging, slogans, and jingles positively impact consumer problem recognition, Nestlé should consistently emphasize these elements in its television advertisements to reinforce awareness and stimulate purchase decisions.

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